

MINERAL-IMPREGNATED CARBON-FIBER (MCF) AS NOVEL ALTERNATIVE TO FIBER-REINFORCED POLYMER (FRP) FOR REINFORCING CONCRETE AND STRUCTURAL SAFETY AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

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ABSTRACT

Mineral-impregnated carbon-fiber (MCF) composites are a promising alternative reinforcement system for building sector. Geopolymer impregnation technology enables efficient industry manufacturing and fast setting times. This paper highlights the load-transferring capacity of MCF in alkali-activated material (AAM) concrete under temperature impact. To meet future market demands, a fully automated processing line is used to fabricate MCF reinforcements. Compared to the epoxy-impregnated reference yarn, enhanced compatibility and comparable bond performance are validated for MCF at 20 °C and considerably improved resistance is attained at elevated temperatures. The potential loss of bond of MCF is attributed mainly to thermal shrinkage of the mineral matrix and concrete.

KEYWORDS

Carbon-fiber composite; mineral impregnation; alkali-activated materials; automated processing; geopolymer.

INTRODUCTION

Reinforced concrete structures with internal carbon-fiber (CF) reinforcements offer a promising alternative to traditional building materials, thanks to the excellent mechanical and durability properties of CFs (Kraft et al., 2022). High temperatures, particularly in fire, greatly reduce the load-bearing capacity of these structures as a consequence of the decomposition of the polymer impregnation matrix of carbon-fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) reinforcements in bar or textile form (Kruppke et al., 2019). For this reason, their service temperature in structural applications is so far limited to 80 °C.

The use of the state of the art thermally-resistant mineral materials, e.g., microcements or geopolymers (GPs) as impregnation mediums is a promising approach, allowing the production of so-called mineral-impregnated carbon fibers (MCF) (Mechtcherine et al., 2020). Unlike polymeric systems, MCF retains its load-transferring capacity even at elevated temperatures up to 500 °C. Furthermore, MCF enables enhanced physical and chemical bonding with cementitious matrix, resulting in finer crack patterns and thereby improving concrete durability. Tremendous, broad innovation potential is also estimated for digital processability, freedom design, ecological and environmental footprints as advantages (Mechtcherine et al., 2021).

Geopolymers (GPs) or alkali-activated materials (AAMs) have emerged as alternative cement-free binders for temperature-resistant fiber reinforced composites and sustainable, fine-grained concrete materials, as proposed in the literature (Zhao et al., 2023a). As impregnation mediums, they offer distinct advantages and structural characteristics, combining features of polymers, ceramics, and cement and indicating a broader processing range for continuous production and rapid setting with high early strength through synthesis at elevated temperature (Zhao et al., 2023b). Potential for chemical bonding at the interfacial region with CF is also reported (Hajimohammadi et al., 2022).

Different from steel reinforcement, the construction of carbon concrete components faces a significant challenge due to the diverse bond behaviour indicated by various profiles of carbon reinforcement. This

discrepancy induces the formation of cracks in the structural element, with crack widths and spacing depending on the type of reinforcement used.

Available information regarding the bonding behavior of fiber-reinforced GP composites with alkali-activated concrete (AAC) are still lacking. To address this gap, this study systematically examined the reinforcing capacity of newly developed MCF in alkali-activated concrete up to 200 °C, comparing it with commercially available carbon yarn impregnated with epoxy resin. MCF production was carried out in a continuous, automated manner. The evaluation of microstructural and morphological characteristics involved environmental scanning electron microscopy (ESEM), and X-ray computed tomography (μ CT).

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Materials and fabrication of mineral-impregnated carbon-fiber (MCF) composites

To fabricate MCF, a carbon tow, SIGRAFIL® C T50-4.4/255-E100, from SGL Group, Germany, was selected, comprising 50,000 individual filaments with a diameter of 6.9 μ m and tensile strength of 4,400 MPa, treated with epoxy sizing. The impregnating suspension included metakaolin (MK) from BASF, Germany, superplasticizer (SP) Sapetin D27 from Woellner, Germany, and potassium silicate activator Geosil® 14517 from Woellner, Germany. Intensive mixing was carried out using a T 50 digital ULTRA-TURRAX® at 7000 rpm for 7 minutes to attain complete impregnation of the filament bundle. The produced metakaolin-based GP impregnation matrix presented a delayed setting time of around 14 h at room temperature without any heat curing. An automated, continuous pultrusion was used to fabricate the unidirectional MCF element with a pulling speed of 6 m/min and pre-wetting before the impregnation processes. Shaping was achieved by two conical nozzles with a 4.1 mm inner opening diameter, as detailed described in (Liebscher et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2021a; Zhao et al., 2021b; Zhao et al., 2023b). To accelerate the hardening process of the matrix, the freshly impregnated yarn elements were sealed and then thermally treated in an electric oven at 50 °C for 16 hours. Figure 1 illustrates both the polymer-impregnated reference reinforcement, the as-received carbon yarn and the finished MCF composites. Cured MCF specimens were stored at 20 °C and 65% relative humidity. The resulting reinforcement had a nearly circular cross-section and a fiber volume fraction of approximately 16 vol.-%. As reference, a commercially available CFRP, GRID Q85/85 - CCE - 21 from Solidian (Albstadt, Germany) was used, impregnated with epoxy (EP) resin and having an average tensile strength of 3300 MPa, E-Modulus of 220 GPa and a glass transition temperature, T_g , of 115 °C.

Figure 1: Polymer-impregnated reference reinforcement, the raw carbon yarn and the finished MCF composites

Characterization of MCF

The bond-slip relationships between the yarn and GP concrete substrate were evaluated using one-sided in-situ pullout tests conducted with an Instron machine (model 8501) equipped with a load cell and Instron climate chamber. The tests were performed at displacement rates of 1 mm/min at room temperature (\sim 20 °C), 100 °C, and 200 °C, following an established testing setup (Zhao et al., 2023c). The AAC matrix applied in the study consisted of MK, ground-granulated blast-furnace slag (GGBS), the same potassium silicate activator (Geosil® 14517), quartz sand, and coarse sand, as interpreted in (Zhao et al., 2023d). Table 1 gives the composition of the mix. In order to mitigate the adverse effects caused by small maximum grain size and a high binder content in modern fine-grained concrete, the particle size distribution of the mixture was carefully adjusted to approximate an ideal target grading curve known as the Fuller parabola. Refer to Figure 2a for a visualization of this approach.

Figure 2b summarizes mechanical properties, including flexural and compressive strengths and Young's modulus of the ambient-cured GP concrete matrix, which were hot-tested at 20 °C, 100 °C

and 200 °C. Elevated environmental temperatures yield in a gradual decrease both in flexural strength and Young's modulus. This decline was attributed to the excessive dehydration of AAM materials and irreversible shrinkage caused by high thermal strains (Zhao et al., 2023d). Whereas, the increasing trend obtained for the compressive strength at higher temperatures might be related to the advancement of the chemical reaction of AAM. Compared to the compressive strength, the flexural strength and Young's modulus are expected to more influence the concrete tensile strength and therewith yarn pull-out behaviour.

Table 1. Mix design of alkali-activated concrete matrix for the yarn pull-out tests and its properties

Concrete composition	Amount [g]
Metakaolin	363.3
Ground-granulated blast-furnace slag	155.7
Fine sand BCS 413	264
Sand 0/2 (Ottendorf)	759
Potassium silicate solution	519
Properties	
Mortar slump flow [mm]	190

Figure 2: (a) Comparison of particle size distribution of the concrete mix and (b) mechanical properties of the AAC matrix under thermal impact

Furthermore, environmental scanning electron microscopy (ESEM) using a Quanta 250 FEG instrument from FEI (The Netherlands) was employed for the morphological analysis. and a micro-computed topographer (μ CT) scan CT-XPRESS from ProCon X-Ray, Germany, equipped with a high-performance 65W X-ray tube and a high-resolution flat panel detector. The specimens for the morphological analysis were prepared by splitting the anchoring parts of the pull-out specimens without damaging the interphase between the yarn and concrete.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Performance of AAC at elevated temperatures

Characterization of impregnating matrix and MCF

Figure 3 shows the pull-out curves and the analysed data for EP yarns and MCFs at both ambient and elevated temperatures. Moreover, Table 2 summarizes the values of debonding strength, τ_d , max. shear strength, τ_{max} , bond modulus, BM, shear stress at a slip of 0.5 mm, $\tau_{0.5}$, and shear stress at a slip of 1.0 mm, τ_1 , and Temperature Influence Factor (TIF). The TIF serves as a correlation factor between the values of τ_{max} obtained at elevated temperatures and their respective values at ambient temperature. The

subsequent sections thoroughly discuss and analyze the test results, focusing on the role of the impregnation material and temperature conditions.

Figure 3: Representative pullout force-displacement curves obtained by pullout tests at different temperatures for (a) EP yarns and (b) MCFs in AAC matrix as well as (c) their respective max. pullout force.

Table 2: Results obtained from the pull-out tests depending on various testing temperatures (average values; standard deviations in parenthesis).

Temp.	Yarn types	τ_d (MPa)	τ_{max} (MPa)	TIF	BM (MPa/mm)	$\tau_{0.5}$ (MPa)	$\tau_{1.0}$ (MPa)
20 °C	EP	11.04 (2.91)	11.04 (2.91)	1	14.36 (1.38)	7.29 (1.57)	8.08 (0.53)
	MCF	4.75 (2.00)	6.37 (1.94)	1	19.10 (3.26)	5.12 (0.72)	5.80 (0.32)
100 °C	EP	7.54 (1.88)	7.54 (1.88)	0.67	11.57 (2.89)	6.60 (3.56)	7.69 (2.15)
	MCF	4.36 (1.99)	4.36 (1.99)	0.68	15.03 (6.20)	3.10 (0.87)	3.37 (0.65)
200 °C	EP	0.11 (0.09)	0.11 (0.09)	0.01	3.42 (0.56)	0.10 (0.08)	0.11 (0.10)
	MCF	3.11 (0.78)	3.11 (0.78)	0.49	9.12 (0.12)	2.61 (0.23)	2.61 (0.24)

Role of yarn variation

Clear differences in pull-out curve profiles are distinguishable among the EP yarns and MCFs, in which the reference EP yarn followed a classical three-part sequence for textile-reinforced concrete, as described in (Lorenz et al., 2013). The initial and nonlinearly ascending branch before reaching the maximum pull-out force is identified by a lower slope and thereby a moderate bond modulus, attributed to the lack of accumulation of reaction products in the interphase between the concrete matrix and the inert CFRP bar. This is followed by a gradual decay of the frictional force in the pullout phase until it was reduced to zero, with slight rises caused by additional friction and bearing stresses from pronounced mechanical interlocks of the wrap-knitting texture on the yarn surface and a high stiffness of EP impregnation.

Compared to the EP yarns, the present results depict similar bond strength, τ_{max} , higher BM and slightly lower energy absorption capacities, $\tau_{0.5}$ and $\tau_{1.0}$ at small crack widths with AAC in the post-peak phase for the newly developed MCF composites. The MCF curve profile highlights a more rapidly increasing branch during the initial loading stage until reaching the peak debonding force at a smaller displacement, indicating a higher shear modulus. Subsequently, a sudden drop is attained, corresponding to adhesive bond failure and fracture in the outer filaments (see Figure 4b). The initial nearly linear-elastic rise transformed into a non-linear path with a decreasing slope before reaching the peak, suggesting a gradual delamination process of the MCF from the matrix. The pullout process of MCF was characterized by a very slowly decreasing branch or even slightly higher stress plateau, dominated by the friction and evident form interlock.

Role of temperature impact

With increasing temperature, TIF values and other parameters including τ_d , τ_{max} , BM, $\tau_{0.5}$, and τ_1 reveal a drop both for EP and MCF yarns, while maintaining similar debonding manners to the cases at 20 °C. The exposure of EP yarns to 100 °C shows an acceptable reduction in bond strength by 33% due to the remaining form interlocks, while further heating to 200 °C results in a complete loss of 99%, consistent with previous findings for FRP with polymer impregnation (Silva et al., 2022). The softening of the viscoelastic epoxy and degradation of the EP matrix's shear modulus beyond its glass transition temperature lead to a noticeable decrease in frictional bonding and mechanical interlock during the pull-out process (Younes et al., 2013).

Similarly, a gradual drop in adhesion strength, bond modulus, and shear stress in the pullout phase with increasing temperature is also attained in the case of MCF. However, MCFs experience a significantly improved temperature resistance, associated with 32% and 51% reductions in bond strength, respectively, as indicated by TIFs. Similar trends are attained as well for the $\tau_{0.5}$, $\tau_{1.0}$, during the post-peak stage and BM values for both yarn variants. Overall, the load transfer capacity of CF reinforcement based on mineral matrices, related to the debonding failure of the boundary filament layers under temperature loading depends on several factors: i) temperature resistance of the impregnation matrix and the concrete portion regarding their volumetric changes; ii) thermal stability of the adhesion between the MCF and concrete substrate; iii) difference in thermal expansion coefficients between the carbon yarn and concrete in the axial direction. Compared to the melting effect of the polymer matrix, thermal strains induced by shrinkage show a lesser impact on the strength and stiffness of the AAC matrix and the transverse stiffness of the MCF.

Failure morphology and analyses

In the conducted experiments, all specimens disclose pull-out failure without any visible signs of concrete splitting or bar rupture, which aligned with the anticipated mode. After failure, the samples were cut off to examine the surfaces of the pullout channels in the concrete matrix tests conducted at room temperature (cf. Figure 4). The EP yarn displays a clean pullout channel without any visible residual fibers, indicating weak chemical compatibility with the AAC matrix. These characteristics can adequately account for the presence of multiple regions with increasing shear stress in the pullout mode and the relatively low bond modulus at 20 °C. However, for MCFs, bond failure predominantly occurs within the reinforcement element due to the potential disruption of the shear-transmitting GP impregnation matrix by chemically incompatible carbon filaments. Residual fibers from the outer layer of the MCF are attached to the pull-out channel, resulting in few concrete destructions. Near the failed MCF surface, scratches on the impregnation matrix and fiber fractures can be seen, highlighting good chemical compatibility with the AAC matrix.

As seen in Figure 4c considerable, temperature-dependent reductions in yarn diameter are assigned to the EP reference yarn, accompanied by drops of 8.5% and 16.0% at 100 °C and 200 °C, respectively. Conversely, the MCF specimens present lower average decreases of approximately 1.0% and 1.8% for 100 °C and 200 °C.

Figure 4: Optical microscope images from the pull-out channels of the (a) EP yarns and (b) smooth MCF at 20 °C and (c) corresponding reductions of yarn diameter under temperature impact.

ESEM images show well-embedded filaments within the impregnation matrix prior to the damage both for the EP reference yarn and MCF, see Figure 5, indicating effective transverse confinement from the

concrete, enabling full utilization of mechanical interlocking and favorable chemical bonding with the AAM concrete. Furthermore, in the case of MCF counterparts, the outer filament layer is also seamlessly surrounded by AAM concrete matrix without visible boundaries at 20 °C. The mutual solubility of these similar materials may lead to the formation of a transition interdiffusion boundary through assimilation. Microscopic observations of the EP yarns reveal few crack growth in the bond zone as the temperature increased, indicating the partially debonded interface between the reinforcement and the concrete and confirming the thermal degradation of the EP coating. For MCFs at 200 °C, premature interfacial cracking also occurred but mainly within a few microns of the outer layer of filaments near the boundary layer. Inevitable minor cracks in the AAC and GP impregnation matrix are observed due to autogenous and drying shrinkage. Their size and shape increased as the temperature was raised from 20 °C to 200 °C.

In the axial direction, the morphology of the MCF bar, captured using μ CT, implies a smooth interface without visible interfacial cracks at room temperature; cf. Figure 5c. After exposure to 200°C, the grey zone between the yarn and the matrix decreases and areas with low density (black) at the interface are more pronounced, representing voids and suggesting debonding cracks axially. These thermal shrinkage-induced premature damages during preheating in the concrete matrix and the reinforcement, particularly near the boundary zone, are the main challenge for the MCF, inducing diminished bond stress. Additionally, the shrinkage of the AAM concrete matrix would reduce compaction pressure towards the reinforcement, decreasing the interfacial intact area as well as therewith the chemical and frictional bond potentially.

Figure 5: ESEM images of the cross-sections of (a,b) EP yarn and (c,d) MCF, at 20 °C and 200 °C (The color sequence of ESEM from dark to light represents the pristine CFs or epoxy resin, GP impregnation

matrix, concrete binder materials, and concrete aggregate, respectively); (e,f) μ CT slices of the pull-out specimens with MCF at 20 °C and 200 °C.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUMMARY

The paper at hand highlights the potential of durable, sustainable and lightweight construction utilizing a combination of alternative reinforcement systems with cement-free AAM concrete matrix. The purposefully designed AAM concrete matrix allows high thermal resistance and mechanical performance without significantly compromising processability. As a novel reinforcement type, mineral-impregnated carbon fibers (MCF) based on a unique, fast-setting forming treatment were manufactured in an automated, continuous pultrusion process.

Evaluation of the bond quality of the MCFs in the AAM concrete matrix demonstrated comparable performance to commercial CF yarns impregnated with epoxy resin at ambient temperature, as well as a significant enhancement at elevated temperatures. Approximately 50% of the bond strength was preserved up to 200 °C. The MCF shows a distinct bonding mechanism to the EP reference yarn, in which the chemical adhesion is enhanced, indicated by pull-out curve profiles. Microscopic and microtomography observations have proven the premature debonding damages between the reinforcement and AAM matrix during preheating, primarily contributing to the degradation of the bond quality of the MCF. Anticipated softening behavior of EP results in the loss of bond strength for the polymer-impregnated yarn at elevated temperatures.

In summary, the application of the proposed MCF prototype as alternative reinforcement for AAM concrete matrices offers a viable technique to minimize the carbon footprint and CO₂ emissions of the built environment and deal with the fire safety of carbon-reinforced concrete. Challenges related to controlled thermal shrinkage and moisture conditions need to be further explored in the future.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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